

A Study on Influences of *Bhouna* in change the Children Habites in Assamese Society

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Abstract

Srimanta Sankardeva, the great Assamese saint and social reformer, who initiated the neo-vaishnavite religious trend in Assam, used many tools to spread his philosophy among common people in 15th and 16th century. Borgeet, Ankianaat are the most popular among them. Sankardeva established *Satras*, as a seat of religious learning and as residential school. He started a trend to play Ankianaat by trained *Bhakats* of *Satras* in *Naamghar*, the religious hall of the villages to motivate villagers for neo-vaishnavism trend. Up to 19th century play Ankiabhaona confined only by trained *Bhakats* of *Satras*. In first phase of 20th century, few cultural reformers started a trend to play AnkiNaat by village children, which have started a new trend of spreading vaishnavism concept and help in change of moral behaviour of the children of Assam.

Trained *Bhakats* of *Satras* were invited to train the children and during the practice period *Bhakats* taught disciplinary cultures and rules of *Satras* to children of villages. During our preliminary survey, we noticed that children, those learn this culture, they have some unique polite manner. Through this paper, we are going to focus on behavioral changes and attitude of trained childrens under *Bhakats* of *Satras*.

Keywords

Neo-Vaishnavism, Satra, Namghar, Bhakat, Attitude, Moral Behavior.

Introduction

SrimantaSankardev was an Assamese polymath of the 15th -16th century who was a saint-scholar, poet, playwright, dancer, actor, musician, artist, socio-religious reformer and significant figure in the cultural history of Assam. He initiated the *Neo-vaishnavite* movement in Assam. For spreading the concept of *Neo-vishnavism* among illiterate Assamese people he used many cultural tools like songs, drama, dance etc. SrimantaSankardev started a unique residential schooling system known as *Satras*. The *Satra* culture evolved coincidentally with folk culture as a consequence of *Neo-Vaiṣṇavite* movement in Assam. The *Satra* institution being formed under the leadership of MahapurūṣhŚaṅkaradeva during the mid-part of Ahom rule transformed Political Assam into a cultural Assam. As a consequence of the *Neo-Vaiṣṇavite* movement, Assam becomes a part of cultural India, though she was far away from political India. For spreading his concept and reform villagers he established another institution known as *Namghar*, where villagers take part in religious activities, cultural activities and discussion with saints of *Satras*.

Among different cultural tools, *AnkiNaat* was an important initiative that Sankardev introduced. The *AnkiyaNaat* is a new genre of plays written in Sanskrit and a literary idiom called Brajabuli. These dramas were composed by Sankardev between 1518 and 1568. Five of them are drawn from the BhāgavataPurāna and the sixth from the *Rāmāyana*. Although they were to familiarize people with the greatness and the antics of lord *Kriṣṇa* and to propagate *Neo-Vaiṣṇavism*, deeper analysis reveals certain moral values imbedded in them.

AnkiyaNaat denotes one-act plays while *Bhaona* is the performance of these plays. These *AnkiyaNaat* always carried a religious message and their enactment showed the victory of good over evil. It is a traditional theatre form which shows the victory of truth at the climax,

generally using mythological figures drawn from the Bhagavata and the Ramayana. He wrote six *AnkiaNaat* like, *Kaliya Daman*, *Patni Prasad*, *KeliGopal*, *Rukmini Haran*, *Parijat Haran* and *Ram Bijay*. The staging of the *Bhaona* in *Satras* and *Naamghar* attracted people in large numbers and may have served as a vehicle for value education, which was imbibed by young and old, and helped form the moral fabric of society at that time. Trained *Bhakats* of *Satras* come or invited by villagers to their villages to train their children in their *Naamghar*.

Attitude that determines how children react to adversity, overcome challenges, create bonds with others and how they learn. It has an important role to play in defining a child's later life outcomes – for example, how they will perform on a personal level in school, the wider social world and at work. It is attitude that determines how children react to adversity, overcome challenges, create bonds with others and how they learn. During our survey in different villages of Assam specially in Majuli, Lakhimpur, Dhemaji and Jorhatdistrict of Assam, we noticed marked attitude change among the children, who take part in *AnkiaNaat* under the guidance of saints (*Bhakats*) of *Satras*.

Objective of study To find out the changes of children attitude with the impact of *AnkiaNaat* in the Assamese Society.

Review of Literature

DulalHazarika, Dr. Mrinal Jyoti Goswami (2019) studied on Reflection of Medieval Assamese society in *AnkiaBhaona: A Study*. The objective of the study is to attempt to test the impact of society in *Bhaona* performance. The Author cannot neglect the influence of society. In indirect or direct form, the influence of society reflected in literature. Sankardev is also not an exception to this. Reflection of contemporary society is seen in the *Ankiya Nat*. With the practical purpose for society, Shankardev arranged for the promotion of *Besnava* religion and as the medium for this purpose, he used drama. In that case, the development of the story or the development of the event in the *Anakiya* drama was interrupted. The objectives of the play's composition also often disrupted the presence of society. Although Sankardev's social life played a pivotal role in the development of the play. The change of society played an important role in the transformation of drama. As Assam entered the modern era, entertainment elements became widely used in *Bhaona*. In the present day, the phenomenon of society has changed the eyebrows in a very strong way. *Bhaona* is coming away from the old times and moving closer to the modern drama. This is an important question as to whether *Anakiya* drama is capable of making an official introduction to future Assam.

Ms. MinakshiHazarika (2019) studied on *AssameseBhaona: A Cultural Appraisal*. This study intends to-a. examine the position and significance of *Bhaona* in Assamese society, b. analyse the changes in *Bhaona* performance, c. examine the role of *Bhaona* competition to maintain the tradition of the performance. The findings of the *areBhaona* was created by Sankaradeva as a medium to preach *Neo-Vaisnavism*. It appears in present days in the folk form of a *MatribhasharBhaona* in Assam. *MatribhasharBhaona* is more popular than *AnkiyaBhaona*, but the performance of *AnkiyaBhaona* occasionally takes place in the villages of Assam. *Bhaona* has gone through several structural changes. These are observed in case of space, time, skill of performance, costume, music etc. New addition to all these has given a new flavour to *MatribhasharBhaona*.

Jyotishman Das (2019), studied on *AnkiyaBhaona and Its Impact on the Socio-Cultural Life of Assam*. The objectives of the study are Most of the Studies on *AnkiyaNaat* focused only on the literary and cultural value of *AnkiyaNaat*. But in this study it is aimed to find its impact on Assamese society through sociological perspective. Sankardev was the pioneer of The Cultural Renaissance of Medieval Assam and *AnkiyaBhaona* was one on his notable creations, which has a great contribution towards each dimension of Assamese Culture and Society. These contributions of *AnkiyaBhaona* are discussed in this paper. *AnkiyaBhaona* is a great tradition of Assam. It should be preserved and practiced. The study is aimed at increasing consciousness of the people about the importance of *Ankiyabhaona* in Assamese Culture. it is seen that the impact of *AnkiyaBhaona* on the socio-religious and cultural life of medieval Assam is noteworthy. *AnkiyaBhaona* played a revolutionary role in the cultural renaissance of medieval Assam through its impact on each dimension of Assamese Society including Language, Literature and Culture. Deep study in this field may discover new dimension of Cultural history of Assam.

Methodology

During our survey, we used personal interview and observational learning techniques. We took personal interview with children who took part in *AnkiaNaat* under the guidance of *Bhakats* of *Satras*, those who have not participated in such and with their parents. We also observed their activities and behaviour with their parents, friends, elders, younger and guest.

Result and Discussion

From our survey, qualities those we consider important for our children have gained from the training of *AnkiaNaat* under the *Bhakats* are responsibility, contentment, appreciation, self-control, concern for others and living life in community.

1. Responsibility: A child who has learned to be responsible from a young age will not shirk from it when he is older. Responsibility means that you take on a job and are happy to be accountable for it and take the consequences if something goes wrong. The temptation, of course, is to blame someone else when there is a problem and that is a habit we should resist. During their course of training of *AnkiaNaat* under *Bhakats*, trained children have gained this quality to be responsible for their duties, timing and practices.

2. Contentment: From an early age, we need to remind ourselves and our children that it is not helpful to compare yourself to others. Trained children have this quality to be content for their own capabilities. After preliminary training period *Bhakats* have selected children on the basis of their capabilities of performance in different activities of *AnkiaNaat*. Those who can play musical instruments and can sing, they are assigned for *Gayan-Bayan*, those can perform well in dancing and acting, they are assigned for play role in *Bhaona*. Children do not argue with other, they just follow the order of *Bhakat* and be happy and try their best to perform their part.

3. Appreciation: Appreciating means to recognize and express how good someone or something is and to value him, her or it. We noticed this character among the trained children more than the untrained children. During the course of training of *AnkiaNaat*, they discuss with their friends about their activities and performance in a positive manner. Parents also informed us that their children regularly appreciate about activities of their friends.

4. Self-Controlled: One of the big changes that parent noticed is the change in control over children's own duties. Before the training, parents were control their timing of food, school timing, bedtime etc. But, when they started the training under *Bhakat* of *Satra*, children become self-controlled on their own regular duties. Few parents very happily informed that their children have started regular prayer and help them in their different household activities.

5. Concern for others: We have noticed that, although children of villages are studying in different schools during the training period they have gained the attitude of concerning for other partners in different directions, eg. those are assigned for playing musical instruments, they share his knowledge with children those are assigned for acting. Those become expert in quick time, they start to support lazy children in break time. Children wear traditional Assamese dress (*Dhuti-Kurta*) in training period. They help each other in dressing. This is a good attitude that children gain in training period of *AnkiaNaat* training period.

6. Living life in community: Children recognize that although in some ways they are independent, they are never alone. Before the training, *Bhakat* asks children to clean the *Naamghar* and praying altogether. These habits help children to be communal in social life. Parents also noticed this attitude among the children and become very happy.

In general, cultivating responsibility, self-control, concern for others, and willingness to live in community take time, but through the training under *Bhakat* of *Satras*, children who take part in *AnkiaNaat* these lessons are gained and keep believe on these nature for future life. Children can learn to behave in a socially approved manner through trial and error, through direct teaching, or through identification. In trial and error learning children try out one behavior after the other to see which gains social approval for them. Eventually, after many trials, they hit upon a behaviour that gives them the desired approval. In direct teaching, children learn to behave in socially approved manner in one situation and then transfer this learning to similar situations. However, if the objective aspects of the situation differ, they fail to see how their learnt behavior can apply to this other situation. In identification, children identify with people they admire and imitate the pattern of behavior they observe in these people. This is usually occurs unconsciously and without pressure from others. Identification as a source of learning moral behavior becomes increasingly important as children grow older. Considering the progressive stages through which moral behavior develops and the significant importance of direct learning and identification in the development of morality, any event which leads the child to observe moral behavior and thereby internalize it would probably facilitate the development of moral values.

After creating this type of moral behavior in the child's mind, they feel about the concept of "God". God is the highest power for every human being. They begin to self-realization about the activities of God from the AnkiNaat. It happens their mind full curiosity and creates positive thinking in their mind. Slowly, their self-realization creates the spiritual education in their mind. This moral and spiritual education helps every human being to take good and perfect decision in their life.

Conclusion

In conclusion it may be stated that the targets of *SrimantaSankardeva* become very successful to change the attitude, social and moral behavior of Assamese community. Stories of *AnkiNaat* help to start trend of *Neo-Vaishnavism* among the Assamese people, that *Iswar* (God) is the super power of the world, we should keep belief on him and to be loyal upon God. We have noticed this belief among the children and noticed progressive change in their attitude and characteristics. These plays are very helpful for children to increase experience and knowledge in personal and social life.

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